

CERTIFICATE OF APPRECIATION

THIS CERTIFIES THAT
TAFAKKUR MANZILI
JURNALIDA FAOL ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN

G'ulomjonov Abdurasul G'ofurjon o'g'li

MODERN METHODS IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES

NOMLI MAQOLASI BILAN ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN TAQDIRLANADI

2023/IYUL

